

ONA TILINI IKKINCHI TIL O'RGANISHDAGI AHAMIYATI.

Dushatova Shohsanam,

FarDU o'qituvchi

Azimova Hilola,

FarDU 3-bosqich talabasi

sh.dushatova@pf.fdu.uz

Annotatsiya: Til inson hayotining muhim qismini ko'rsatadi. Til atrofdagi narsalarni tushunishga, tushunchalarni o'rganishga va bir nechta ko'nikmalarga erishishga yordam beradi. Ushbu maqolada ona tilining jamiyatda muhim ekani va bolalarga yoshlikdan o'z ona tillarini yaxshi o'rgatishning foydalari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: vosita, tushuncha, ko'nikma, jarayon, muloqot.

Abstract: Language shows an important part of human life. Language helps us to understand our surroundings, learn concepts and acquire several skills. This article discusses the importance of the mother tongue in society and the benefits of teaching children their mother tongue well from a young age.

Key words: tool, concept, skill, process, communication.

Аннотация: Язык показывает важную часть жизни человека. Язык помогает нам понять наше окружение, изучить понятия и приобрести некоторые навыки. В этой статье обсуждается важность родного языка в обществе и преимущества обучения детей родному языку с раннего возраста.

Ключевые слова: инструмент, концепция, умение, процесс, общение.

Ona tili - bu bolaligida o'rganadigan birinchi til, bolaligida biladigan til. Ona tili odamlarning fikrlash va his-tuyg'ularini shakllantirishda markaziy o'rin tutadi. Ona tili odamlarda bilim olishning ta'sirchan vositasidir.

Til inson hayotining muhim qismini ko'rsatadi. Til atrofdagi narsalarni tushunishga, tushunchalarni o'rganishga va bir nechta ko'nikmalarga erishishga yordam beradi. O'z ona tilini yaxshi bilgan bola o'zini ifoda etish va fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan til ko'nikmalarini yaxshilaydi. Bundan tashqari, bu til boshqa narsalarni o'rganishda bolada ishonch va o'zini o'zi qadrlash tuyg'usini rivojlantiradi.

Ona tili har bir inson uchun qadrlidir. Ona tili insonlarning tafakkuri va hissiyotlarini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bolaning har tomonlama rivojlanishi uchun ona tilida gapirishni o'rganish juda zarur. O'z ona tilini bilish boshqa tillarni o'rganishga ham katta yordam beradi. Bola dunyoga kelishidan avval onasining muloqotini eshitish orqali atrofida nima borligini tushunadi, anglaydi.

Ona tili shaxsiy va madaniy o'ziga xoslikni rivojlantiradi. Shaxsiy o'ziga xoslik insonning o'zini, atrofini va tarixini tushunishidan kelib chiqadi. Inson ona tilini ona qornida birinchi bo'lib eshitadi va u ongli ravishda uning qarashlari va his-tuyg'ularini aniqlay boshlaydi. Shunday qilib, u oila, jamiyat, madaniyat va o'ziga xoslik bilan aloqa asoslarini rivojlantiradi. Uning mustahkam poydevori ijtimoiy kelib chiqishi va xarakterini eng asosiy va tabiiy tarzda tushunish orqali o'zini kuchli qabul qiladi. Bundan tashqari, jamiyatda so'zlashadigan turli tillarni qo'llab-quvvatlash orqali madaniy o'ziga xoslik paydo bo'ladi.

Ona tilining ahamiyati juda kattadir chunki bolalar o'z ona tilini rivojlantirganda, ular bir vaqtning o'zida tanqidiy fikrlash va savodxonlik kabi boshqa muhim ko'nikmalarni ham rivojlantiradilar.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'z ona tilini yaxshi biladigan odamlarda intellektual rivojlanish nisbatan tezroq kechadi.

Erta savodxonlik ko'nikmalarini muvaffaqiyatli o'rgatish nafaqat tegishli materiallar bilan ta'minlashga, balki ushbu ko'nikmalarni joriy etish va o'rgatish usullariga ham bog'liq. Darslikka e'tibor qaratgan holda eslab o'rganish va yodlash bolaning ravon o'qishiga yordam beradi. O'qituvchilar bolalar o'quv jarayonida faol bo'lgan qiziqarli ta'lim strategiyalaridan foydalanishlari kerak.

Ta'lim sifatini oshirish uchun til siyosatida ona tilini o'rganishni hisobga olish kerak. Dastlabki yillarda ona tiliga e'tibor bermagan ta'lim modellari samarasiz bo'lishi va bolalarning bilim olishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Ona tilidagi ta'lim hech bo'lmaganda dastlabki yillarda o'qituvchilarga ta'lim berishga, o'quvchilarga esa yanada samaraliroq o'rganishga imkon beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Berliner, DC (2006). Our impoverished view of educational research. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 949–995. Publisher Full Text
2. Borman, GD, & Kimball, SM (2005). Teacher quality and educational quality: Do teachers with higher standards-based evaluation ratings close student achievement gaps? *The Elementary School Journal*, 106(1), 3–20. Publisher Full Text
3. Bray, M (2003). Adverse Effects of Supplementary Private Tutoring: Dimensions, Implications, and Government Responses.
4. Dushatova, S. (2022). LINGUISTIC AND SOCIAL ORIGINATION OF TABOOS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 318-321.
5. Dushatova, S., & Tursunaliyev, M. (2022). CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHNING INSON RIVOJLANISHIGA TASIRI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 133-138.
6. Dushatova, S., & Azamov, M. (2022, November). SO'Z TURKUMLARI TASNIFI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 89-95).
7. Shokhsanam, D., & Abdukarimova, M. (2022, December). THE ADVANTAGES OF BOOKS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE DEDICATED TO THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY* (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 169-171).

8. Aliyeva, N. (2021). Similarities And Distinctive Features Of Uzbek, Russian And English Phrases. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(05), 315-321.
9. Alieva, N. (2022). The Use of New Phraseological Units and Collocations in the Language. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 66-72.
10. Aliyeva, N. (2021). Modern concepts of the study of phraseological units within the framework of frame representation and the theory of conceptual metaphor. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(4), 147-156.
11. Aliyeva, N. (2021). MODERN CONCEPTS OF STUDYING PHRASEOLOGISMS IN THE FRAMEWORK OF FRAME REPRESENTATION AND THEORY OF CONCEPTUAL METAPHOR. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758)*, 2(12), 206-211.
12. Zafar, J. (2022). Linguistic and Cultural Problems in Translation. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(12), 55-57.
13. Dushatova, S., & qizi Norinboyeva, D. J. (2022). CHET TILIDA NUTQNI TINGLAB TUSHUNISH VA UNDA FRAZEOLOGIZMLARNING O'RNI. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(7), 66-71.
14. Shokhsanam, D., & Makhmudova, M. (2022). BENEFITS OF DAILY READING. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 28-32.
15. Dushatova, S., & Burgutova, G. (2022). CHET TILLARINI BILISHNING FOYDALARI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 40-45.

16. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & qizi Qodiraliyeva, N. I. (2022). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4, 1(5)*, 63-67.
17. Dushatova, S., & Mamajonova, S. (2022). "ICEBERG PRINCIPLE" AS A STYLISTIC FEATURE OF E. HEMINGWAY'S SHORT STORY "THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA". *Science and innovation, 1(B8)*, 1931-1934.